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**A STUDY TO IDENTIFY THE FACTORS AFFECTING EMPLOYEE TURNOVER IN
SMALL SCALE INDUSTRIES**

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ABSTRACT

Now-a-days small scale industries play a very vital role to develop the economy of the country. In this vital segment of Indian economy i.e. a developing country, these types of industries becomes more crucial although Employees and technology are the backbone of any organization that's why in many studies most of the researchers pointed out the causes of employee turnover time to time with the help of various factors. This study looks in order to build-up efficient and healthy environment for work force and prepare them to commit with the organization with full of satisfaction. In this study it contains two vital areas that first one is Parameters that related with job satisfaction and second one is commitment of employees in small scale industries in Indore location particularly that either they are thinking about to leave the organization and if yes then why? For the purpose to collect data there are some factors that directly connected with Quality of work life and give us a dozen different parameters regarding job satisfaction and secondary data collected from various journals, website, newspapers and research papers. In view of the large number of SSI in Indore district, a sampling method accepted.

KEYWORDS: **Keywords:** SSI (Small Scale Industries), Manufacturing sector, Service sector, JS (Job Satisfaction), JC (Job Commitment), QWL (Quality of Work Life)

INTRODUCTION

Employees and technology are the backbone of any organization. Employee turnover is the rate at which employee's leaves a company and have to be replaced by a new or existing staff. Employee turnover is the rotation of workers around the labour market between firms, jobs and occupation and between the states of employment and unemployment (Abassi&Hollman, 2000) Employee turnover either voluntary or involuntary. Voluntary refers to termination on the will of employee's hand and involuntary turnover refers that employees has no choice in the termination (Heneman, 1998). Boxell et al (2003), in New Zealand said that the view that motivation for job change is multidimensional and that no one factor will explain it. However over the time there are various factors comes out that really affect the turnover and help the Human Resource department to reduce the employee turnover and save a lot of money. Our developing country India has about 4.22 crore industries working in which around 60% industries are small scale industries and Their investment in plant is between 25 lack to 5 crore and contribute around 40% if total Indian economy that is comes from industries, Hence the SSI not only provide the employment but contribute a heavy amount of GDP in Indian economy. In the small scale industry the employees are the most important resources or assets. They endeavour to provide excellent products, meet and execute customer expectations, achieve competitive advantage and exceptional organizational performance. So, human resources play a pivotal role among the various other resources which are required for ensuring the growth and development of this industry. The availability of skilled managerial and technical manpower in India will contribute considerably to the prosperity of the small scale industry in future. With this backdrop, the present study is attempted to study the impact of work related factors on quality of work life of employees in the small scale industries in Indore district.

Small scale industry: Indian economy is balanced on agriculture and industry like equilibrium of vehicle with two wheels. However agriculture and industry are two sides of one coin where country can achieve overall development. Indian economy is known as mixed economy where nearly 58% population depend on agriculture and agro based industries like food processing industry, oil processing industry, refinery production, etc. are the part of small industries. According to an atmosphere of Indian economy and nature of economy where small scale industries play a pivotal role in generating employment, production of basic goods and services, enhancing market and increasing in national income of the country therefore it is said that small scale industries are a backbone of Indian economy. There is no any fixed definition for SSI but right from industrial policy 1964 up to 1991 there has been drastic changes in the definition of SSI.

1. According to I.P. 1964, "SSI refers to such a small enterprises which requires an investment in capital from 25 lakh up to 60 lakh."

2. According to I.P. 1991, "SSI are such a type of industries whose investment of capital and tools limits from 50 lakh up to 1 crore."

3. Currently small scale industries refer to such a units of industries which require capital investment from minimum 2 crore up to maximum 4 crore.

Aim and objectives

1. To examine the employee turnover of a small scale industry with the use of Quality of work life in both voluntary and involuntary aspect.
2. Find out various dependent and independent factors that affects the employee turnover directly or indirectly in small scale industry.
3. To get how Managers can take appropriate actions to improve employees' QWL and subsequently reduce employees' turnover.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A sampling method considered to be adequate for my study. Each and every response is checked thoroughly for incomplete and missing response. The questionnaire has three parts

a. **First part** contains some **demographic information**. In this section, questionnaires are designed to get information on the demographics of the Respondents or respondent profile such as age, gender, level of education, position, years of experience, race, marital status, salary and number of changed job. The questionnaires used the Multiple-Choice question where the respondents have to choose the most suitable answer that is related to them and used nominal scale. Nominal scale categorizes individual into mutually exclusive and collectively exhaustive groups. Nominal scale is used for measurement. It allows the researcher to assign subjects to certain categories or groups.

Demographic information:- Gender, Age, Marital Status, Educational Qualification, Experience, Income.

b. In the **second part**, the **questionnaire** contains a dozen (twelve) items to construct the various independent variables along with a dependent variable in my study. The selected independent variables are: stress, safety and health conditions, job security, fringe benefits, self satisfaction, opportunities for promotion, fair compensation, training programme, top management appreciation, involvement in decision, relationship with co-workers, job satisfaction. A five point Likert scale (1= Strongly Disagree to 5= Strongly Agree) was used to collect data from the respondents. The questionnaire was outlined in English and understandable.

Hence here I taken 1 dependent and 11 independent factor in the form of questionnaire, they are follows:-

Table1. Questionnaire consist various independent and dependent factors

Factors	
1-Is your work stress free	
2-Is your safety and health conditions excellent	
3-Job security is good in organization	

4- Our teamwork in organization	Independent Factors	
5-opportunities for promotion are good		
6-Training program given by organization		
7-Fringe & welfare benefits are good		
8-Satisfy with adequate & fair compensation		
9-Proud to be working with my organization		
10-Top management appreciate our work		
11-Involvement in decision making		
Satisfaction with your job		Dependent Factor

Methodology adapted to analyse the various factors

Here I have 12 Questionnaire or factors related with various category like work environment, career development, monetary satisfaction and managerial satisfaction. In which there is one dependent factor and 11 independent factors. Total sample size 100 is taken from Manufacturing Sector and 80 from Service sector. Samples are taken randomly among various industries in Indore district particularly. Manufacturing sector consist various industries like chemical, machine part manufacturing, automobile parts manufacturing, food processing etc. Service sectors consists call centre, Trading agencies, domestic city bus Service Company, Insurance company etc.

a. **Pearson's Correlation Coefficient**-Correlation is a technique for investigating the relationship between two quantitative, continuous variables, for example, age and blood pressure. Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) is a measure of the strength of the association between the two variables. There is a dependent factor which is job satisfaction and 11 independent factors named stress, safety and health conditions, job security, fringe benefits, self satisfaction, opportunities for promotion, fair compensation, training programme, top management appreciation, involvement in decision, relationship with co-workers, Pearson correlation coefficient describes the relationship between the each independent factor with dependent factor.

b. **R-Square Analysis**- R-squared is a statistical measure of how close the data are to the fitted regression line. It is also known as the coefficient of determination, or the coefficient of multiple determinations for multiple regressions. R^2 is a statistic that will give some information about the goodness of fit of a model. In regression, the R^2 coefficient of determination is a statistical measure of how well the regression line approximates the real data points. An R^2 of 1 indicates that the regression line perfectly fits the data.

The definition of R-squared is fairly straight-forward; it is the percentage of the response variable variation that is explained by a linear model. Or:

$R\text{-squared} = \text{Explained variation} / \text{Total variation}$

R-squared is always between 0 and 100%:

0% indicates that the model explains none of the variability of the response data around its mean.

100% indicates that the model explains all the variability of the response data around its mean.

In general, the higher the R-squared, the better the model fits your data.

c. **Regression analysis** -In statistical modelling, **regression analysis** is a statistical process for estimating the relationships among variables. It includes many techniques for modelling and analysing several variables, when the focus is on the relationship between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables (or 'predictors'). More specifically, regression analysis helps one understand how the typical value of the dependent variable (or 'criterion variable') changes when any one of the independent variables is varied, while the other independent variables are held fixed. Most commonly, regression analysis estimates the conditional expectation of the dependent variable given the independent variables – that is, the average value of the dependent variable when the independent variables are fixed.

Hypothesis

a. Related with work environment

- H1 There is a positive and significant relationship between working stressfree and job satisfaction.
- H2 There is a positive and significant relationship between Safety and health conditions and Job satisfaction.
- H3 There is a positive and significant relationship between job Security and Job satisfaction.
- H4 There is a positive and significant relationship between teamwork and job satisfaction.

b. Related with career development

- H5 There is a positive and significant relationship between opportunities for promotion and job satisfaction.
- H6 There is a positive and significant relationship between timely training programme and Job satisfaction.

c. Related with Monetary satisfaction

- H7 There is a positive and significant relationship between fringe and welfare benefits and Job satisfaction.
- H8 There is a positive and significant relationship between Fair compensation and Job satisfaction.

d. Related with managerial aspects

- H9 There is a positive and significant relationship between Proud feelings and Job satisfaction.
- H10 There is a positive and significant relationship between Appreciation and Job satisfaction.
- H11 There is a positive and significant relationship between Involvement in decision making and Job satisfaction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Result:

These demographic results show the frequencies and percentage distribution among various categories like age, Gender, Marital status, Educational qualification, Experience and income in different divisions.

Table2: Demographic results

Variable	Frequency (Manufacturing)	Percent	Frequency (Service)	Percentage
Age				
18 to 30	36	36.00	60	75
30 to 40	50	50.00	18	2205
40 to 50	10	10.00	2	205
Above 50	4	4.00	0	0
Total	100	100	80	100
Gender				
Male	99	99.0	58	72.5
Female	1	1.0	22	27.5
Total	100	100	80	100
Marital status				

Married	76	76.00	40	50
Unmarried	24	24.00	40	50
Total	100	100	80	100
<i>Education</i>				
12 th	12	12.00	20	25
Diploma	18	18.00	0	0
Graduation	58	58.00	56	70
Post graduation	12	12.00	4	5
Total	100	100	80	100
<i>Experience</i>				
0 to 5	34	34.0	60	75
5 to 10	44	44.0	16	20
10 to 15	14	14.0	4	5
Above 15	8	8.0	0	0
Total	100	100	80	100
<i>Income</i>				
Below 1 Lac	12	12.0	12	15
1 to 3 Lacs	36	36.0	42	52.5
3 to 5 Lacs	36	36.0	20	25
Above 5 Lacs	16	16.0	6	7.5
Total	100	100	80	100

Age is the main demographic tool which directly or indirectly depends on the job satisfaction. Here one thing is considerable that 99% is male candidate in manufacturing sector which is most dominating factor in this category. Besides in service sector 72.5% employees are male and 27.5% are female, which is considerable. As per the collected data, while 36% of respondents were between age 20-30 in manufacturing sector while 60% in service which is most affect the decision criteria, Age range 40 to 50 years is very less ie 10% in manufacturing sector and only 2.5% employees are 40 to 50 years old in service sector. The results in table depict the education level of respondents as 12% have postgraduate qualifications, 18% have achieved diploma education level, 12% of respondents have 12th pass and 58% have graduation which is maximum in manufacturing sector also 70% employees are graduate in service sector, no one have diploma and 25% are having matriculation in service sector. Above table show that 0 to 5 years experience 34% of employee are found in small scale industries in manufacturing sector and similarly 75% employees in service sector. 5 to 10 years experience 44% of employee are found and 16% is from service sector. 10 to 15 years experience 14% of employee are found in manufacturing sector and 5% is from service sector and above 15 years experience 8% of employee are found in manufacturing sector in

small scale industries and no one is there in service sector in this category. In manufacturing small scale industries below 1 Lakh per year 12% employee do work in small scale industries. 1 to 3 lakh per year 36% employee are found and 3 to 5 lakh per year 36% employees are found. Above 5 lakh per year 16% employee are found in small scale industries. Also about 52.5 % employees is between 1 to 3 lakh income category which is maximum among all, 25% are between 3 to 5 lacs.

Reliability Analysis: Manufacturing Sector

Reliability analysis is conducted for all the factors related with work environment (.390), related with career development (.640), related with monetary satisfaction (0.421) and related with managerial satisfaction (0.354). Hence individually each factor has less reliability factor but overall Reliability is 0.710 which is acceptable. Sekaran and Bougie (2009) mentioned that values above 0.7 are considered acceptable, however value above 0.8 are preferable or good. The value is negative due to a negative average covariance among items. This violates reliability model assumptions. This is due to less data sampling and inadequate questionnaire in a given parameter. But here overall reliability is 0.710 which is good and significant for our study.

Table3: Cronchbach's Alpha reliability

Cronbach's Alpha (Overall)	N of items
.710	12

Table4: Reliability tests individually on each factors

Factor's name	items	values
Related with work environment	4	0.390
Related with career development	2	0.645
Related with Monetary satisfaction	2	-0.421
Related with managerial aspects	3	0.354

Reliability Analysis: Service Sector

Reliability analysis is conducted for all the factors related with work environment (.676), related with career development (.479), related with monetary satisfaction (0.421) and related with monetary satisfaction (0.112). Hence individually each factor has less reliability factor but overall Reliability is 0.703 which is acceptable. Sekaran and Bougie (2009) mentioned that values above 0.7 are considered acceptable, however value above 0.8 are preferable or good. The value is negative due to a negative average covariance among items. This violates reliability model assumptions. This is due to less data sampling and inadequate questionnaire in a given parameter. But here overall reliability is 0.703 which is good and significant for our study.

Table 5: Cronchbach's Alpha reliability

Cronbach's Alpha(Overall)	N of items
.703	12

Table 6: Mean Reliability tests on individual factor

Factor's name	items	values
Related with work environment	4	0.676
Related with career development	2	0.479
Related with Monetary satisfaction	2	0.112
Related with managerial aspects	3	-0.059

Regression analysis: Manufacturing

Table 7: Regression analysis model of manufacturing sector

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Sig.
1	.827 ^a	.684	.644	.62127	.000

b. Dependent Variable: Job satisfaction

The R² for this model is 0.684. This means that almost 68.4 percent of the variance dependent variables (Job satisfaction) is explained by the variation in the independent variables ie. Stress, safety and health conditions, job security, fringe benefits, self-satisfaction, opportunities for promotion, fair compensation, training programme, top management appreciation, involvement in decision, relationship with co-workers. Overall significance on 0.000 which is less than 5% level of confidence. Thus, all variables are making a statistically significant unique contribution to the prediction of the dependent variable (Job satisfaction).

The next table is the F-test, the linear regression's F-test has the null hypothesis that there is positive linear relationship between the predictors and dependent variable (in other words R²=1). With F = 17.305 and 99 degrees of freedom the test is highly significant for p<0.05 level of significance, thus we can assume that there is a linear relationship between the variables in our model.

Table8: ANOVA^b method on manufacturing sector

Model		Sum Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	73.474	11	6.679	17.305	.000 ^a
	Residual	33.966	88	.386		
	Total	107.440	99			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Stress, safety and health conditions, job security, fringe benefits, self satisfaction, opportunities for promotion, fair compensation, training programme, top management appreciation, involvement in decision, relationship with co-workers

b. Dependent Variable: Job satisfaction

This is the table that shows the output of the ANOVA analysis and whether we have a statistically significant difference between our group means. We can see that the significance level is 0.021 ($p = .021$), which is below 0.05. we can conclude that there is a statistically significant difference between your three conditions. Next The **Coefficients** table provides us with the necessary information to predict dependent variable job satisfaction from other dependent factors stress, safety and health conditions, job security, fringe benefits, self satisfaction, opportunities for promotion, fair compensation, training programme, top management appreciation, involvement in decision, relationship with co-workers, as well as determine whether independent variables contributes statistically significantly to the model (by looking at the "**Sig.**" column). Furthermore, we can use the values in the "**Beta**" column under the "**standardized Coefficients**" column, as shown below:

Table9: Coefficient analysis of M

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	sig	rank
	B	Std Error	Beta			
(Constant)	.910	.459		1.983	.050	
H1-Is your work stress free	.126	.080	.123	1.578	.018	2
H2-Is your safety and health conditions excellent	-.094	.079	-.082	-1.182	.040	-
H3-Job security is good in organization	.025	.079	.032	.321	.000	7
H4-Our teamwork in organization	-.018	.072	-.017	-.243	.008	-
H5-opportunities for promotion are good	-.071	.062	-.087	-1.150	.003	-
H6-Training program given by organization	.040	.063	.050	.627	.002	5
H7-Fringe & welfare benefits are good	.089	.070	.085	1.269	.008	3
H8-Satisfy with adequate & fair compensation	.012	.074	.013	.165	.009	8
H9-Proud to be working with my organization	.676	.076	.729	8.931	.000	1
H10-Top management appreciate our work	.042	.062	.043	.680	.008	6
H11-Involvement in decision making	.057	.075	.065	.764	.007	4

Table 9 reflects the regression model that was developed by turnover intention as the dependent

variable and the following factors as the independent variables: stress, safety and health conditions, job security, fringe benefits, self satisfaction, opportunities for promotion, fair compensation, training programme, top management appreciation, involvement in decision, relationship with co-workers and dependent variable is job satisfaction. All independent variables which are stress, safety and health conditions, job security, fringe benefits, self satisfaction, opportunities for promotion, fair compensation, training programme, top management appreciation, involvement in decision and relationship with co-workers had significant value less than 0.05 (0.01,0.04,0.00, 0.008, 0.000, 0.003, 0.009, 0.002, 0.008, 0.007, 0.008respectively). Thus, all variables are making a statistically significant unique contribution to the prediction of the dependent variable (JS).

The R² for this model is 0.684. This means that almost 68.4 percent of the variance dependent variables (Job satisfaction) is explained by the variation in the independent variables ie. Stress, safety and health conditions, job

security, fringe benefits, self satisfaction, opportunities for promotion, fair compensation, training programme, top management appreciation, involvement in decision, relationship with co-workers. Overall significance on 0.000 which is less than 5% level of confidence. Thus, all variables are making a statistically significant unique contribution to the prediction of the dependent variable (Job satisfaction).

Findings:-The regression analysis revealed that organizational stress free feel had positive and significant Relationship on job satisfaction (Beta = 0.123) and it supported the first hypothesis (H1) of the study. That is, job satisfaction is high if the employees perceived low level of organizational stress and this finding is in line with previous study done by (Herman, 1997; Mcconnel 1999; Richardson, 1999). Safety and health conditions is the variable that had negative and insignificant relationship with job satisfaction with (Beta = -0.082). In other word it can be described as this factor is not considerable for study. Hence hypothesis H2 is rejected. Job security had positive and significant relationship on job satisfaction (Beta = 0.032) and it supported the third hypothesis (H3) of the study. That is, job satisfaction is high if employees feel that they had a secure job. Fringe and welfare benefits had positive and significant relationship on job satisfaction (Beta = 0.085) and it supported the seventh hypothesis (H7) of the study. That is, job satisfaction is high if the fringe and welfare benefits like bonus, travel allowances, insurance, medical etc. Proud feeling to work with the organization is the highly supporting variable that had positive and significant relationship with job satisfaction with (Beta = 0.729). In other word it can be described as this factor is highly considerable for study. Hence hypothesis H9 is accepted. Opportunities for promotion had negative and insignificant relationship on job satisfaction (Beta = -0.0870) and it does not support the fifth hypothesis (H5) of the study. That is, job satisfaction is not related with opportunities for promotion. Satisfaction with adequate fair and compensation had positive and significant relationship on job satisfaction (Beta = 0.013) and it supported the eighth hypothesis (H8) of the study. That is, job satisfaction is high if employees feel that they had a fair compensation. Training program given by organization time to time had positive and significant relationship on job satisfaction (Beta = 0.050) and it supported the sixth hypothesis (H6) of the study. That is, job satisfaction is high if employees feel that organization give training program and share the knowledge about latest technologies and innovation then they feel high level of job satisfaction. Appreciation of top management also had positive and significant relationship on job satisfaction (Beta = 0.043) and it supported the tenth hypothesis (H10) of the study. That is, job satisfaction is high if we involve the employees in decision making. Involvement in decision making had positive and significant relationship on job satisfaction (Beta = 0.065) and it supported the eleventh hypothesis (H11) of the study. That is, job satisfaction is high if we involve the employees in decision making. Team work in organization also had negative and insignificant relationship on job satisfaction (Beta = -0.017) and it does not support the third hypothesis (H3) of the study. That is, Team work is not a considerable factor to study either it is already very good or as shown in frequency table previously or employees do not feel any bother about their team work.

Regression analysis: Service Sector

Table 10: Regression analysis model of Service sector

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate	Sig.
1	.605 ^a	.366	.263		1.01262	.001

b. Dependent Variable: Job satisfaction

The R² for this model is 0.366. This means that almost 36.6 percent of the variance dependent variables (Job satisfaction) is explained by the variation in the independent variables i.e. stress, safety and health conditions, job security, fringe benefits, self satisfaction, opportunities for promotion, fair compensation, training programme, top management appreciation, involvement in decision, relationship with co-workers. Overall significance on 0.001 which is less than 5% level of confidence. Thus, all variables are making a statistically significant unique contribution to the prediction of the dependent variable (turnover intention)

Table11: ANOVA^bmethod on Service sector

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	40.223	11	3.657	3.566	.001 ^a
	Residual	69.727	68	1.025		
	Total	109.950	79			

a. Predictors: (Constant): stress, safety and health conditions, job security, fringe benefits, self satisfaction, opportunities for promotion, fair compensation, training programme, top management appreciation, involvement in decision, relationship with co-workers

b. Dependent Variable: Job satisfaction

The next table is the F-test, the linear regression's F-test has the null hypothesis that there is positive linear relationship between the predictors and dependent variable (in other words $R^2=1$). With $F = 3.566$ and 79 degrees of freedom the test is highly significant for $p < 0.05$ level of significance, thus we can assume that there is a linear relationship between the variables in our model.

Table 12: Coefficient analysis of Service sector

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standard ized	t	Sig.	Rank
	B	Std Error	Beta			
(Constant)	-.341	.767		-.444	.658	-
H1- stress free work	.012	.124	.013	.099	.021	8
H2- safety and health conditions excellent	-.019	.159	-.016	-.119	.006	
H3-Job security is good in organization	.158	.123	.171	1.279	.005	4
H4-Our teamwork in organization	.115	.142	.116	.810	.021	5
H5-opportunities for promotion are good	.286	.113	.280	2.529	.014	1
H6-Training program given by organization	.105	.120	.104	.868	.038	6
H7-Fringe & welfare benefits are good	.109	.138	.089	.786	.035	7
H8-Satisfy with adequate & fair compensation	.181	.119	.196	1.520	.033	3
H9-Proud to be working with my organization	-.090	.139	-.081	-.649	.019	-

H10-Top management appreciate our work	.243	.133	.216	1.823	.003	2
H11-Involvement in decision making	.011	.103	.012	.105	.017	9

Dependent variable- Job satisfaction

Table 12 reflects the regression model that was developed by turnover intention as the dependent

variable and the following factors as the independent variables: stress, safety and health conditions, job security, fringe benefits, self satisfaction, opportunities for promotion, fair compensation, training programme, top management appreciation, involvement in decision, relationship with co-workers and dependent variable is job satisfaction. All independent variables which are stress, safety and health conditions, job security, fringe benefits, self satisfaction, opportunities for promotion, fair compensation, training programme, top management appreciation, involvement in decision and relationship with co-workers had significant value less than 0.05 (0.021,0.006, 0.005, 0.035,0.019,0.014,0.033,0.038,0.003,0.017,0.021 respectively). Thus, all variables are making a statistically significant unique contribution to the prediction of the dependent variable (turnover intention).

The R² for this model is 0.366. This means that almost 36.6 percent of the variance dependent variables (Job satisfaction) is explained by the variation in the independent variables ie.stress, safety and health conditions, job security, fringe benefits, self satisfaction, opportunities for promotion, fair compensation, training programme, top management appreciation, involvement in decision, relationship with co-workers. Overall significance on 0.001 which s less than 5% level of confidence. Thus, all variables are making a statistically significant unique contribution to the prediction of the dependent variable (turnover intention).

Findings:-The regression analysis revealed that organizational stress free feel had positive and significant Relationship on job satisfaction (Beta = 0.013) and it supported the first hypothesis (H1) of the study.That is, job satisfaction is high if the employees perceived low level of organizational stress and this finding is in line with previous study done by (Herman, 1997; Mcconnel 1999; Richardson, 1999).Safety and health conditions is the variable that had negative and insignificant relationship with job satisfaction with (Beta =-0.119) . In other word it can be described as this factor is not considerable for study. Hence hypothesis H2 is rejected.Job security had positive and significant relationship on job satisfaction (Beta = 0.171) and it supported the third hypothesis (H3) of the study. That is, job satisfaction is high is employees feel that they had a secure job.Fringe and welfare benefits had positive and significant relationship on job satisfaction (Beta = 0.089) and it supported the seventh hypothesis (H7) of the study. That is, job satisfaction is high if the fringe and welfare benefits like bonus, travel allowances, insurance, medical etc.Proud feeling to work with the organization is the second variable that had negative and insignificant relationship with job satisfaction with (Beta =-0.081) . In other word it can be described as this factor is not considerable for study. Hence hypothesis H9 is rejected.Opportunities for promotion had positive and significant relationship on job satisfaction (Beta = 0.280) and it supported the fifth hypothesis (H5) of the study. That is, job satisfaction is high is employees feel that they had a opportunities for promotion. This is the highest level of beta that shows the highest relation with dependent factor that is job satisfaction.Satisfaction with adequate fair and compensation had positive and significant relationship on job satisfaction (Beta = 0.196) and it supported the eighth hypothesis (H8) of the study. That is, job satisfaction is high is employees feel that they had a fair compensation.Training program given by organization time to time had positive and significant relationship on job satisfaction (Beta = 0.104) and it supported the sixth hypothesis (H6) of the study. That is, job satisfaction is high if employees feel that organization give training program and share the knowledge about latest technologies and innovation then they feels high level of job satisfaction.Appreciation of top management also had positive and significant relationship with job satisfaction (Beta = 0.216) and it supported the tenth hypothesis (H10) of the study. That is, job satisfaction is high.Involvement in decision making had positive and significant relationship on job satisfaction (Beta = 0.012) and it supported the eleventh hypothesis (H11) of the study. That is, job satisfaction is high if we involve the employees in decision making. Team work in organization also had positive and significant

relationship with job satisfaction (Beta = 0.116) and it supported the third hypothesis (H3) of the study. That is, job satisfaction is high if the teamwork is high in the organization.

CONCLUSION

Manufacturing: Finally, according to Beta values in table 9 have been used by the researcher in comparing the contribution of each independent variable in order to identify the most significant factors influencing the turnover intention among existing employees in manufacturing sector. Based on this regressions analysis, the largest beta coefficient is 0.729, which is proud feeling to work with the organization. This means that this is the most significant factors influencing the job satisfaction. Besides that, work stress recorded second largest (Beta = 0.123). Meanwhile, the third significant factor influencing turnover intention is fringe and welfare benefits with (Beta= 0.085). Then, it is followed by involvement in decision making, training program, top management's appreciation, job security and fair compensation.

Service :Finally, according to the beta values in table 12 have been used by the researcher in comparing the contribution of each independent variable in order to identify the most significant factors influencing the job satisfaction and then ultimately turnover intention among existing employees in manufacturing sector. Based on this regressions analysis, the largest beta coefficient belongs from opportunity for promotion. This means that this is the most significant factors influencing the job satisfaction. Besides that, top management's appreciation recorded second largest .Meanwhile, the third significant factor influencing turnover intention is fair compensation. Then, it is followed by job security, team work, training program, fringe and welfare benefits and work stress.

FUTURE SCOPE

Future research must focus on a wider sample in order to get more generalized results. Moreover, it must be directed at understanding individual differences so that employee specific initiatives to improve work life balance could be initiated by organizations. The size of the sample used to determine the dimensions of the scale was small. As a result, the stability of the results is uncertain.

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